

Stability Constants of some Y (III)-Complexes from Potentiometric Data

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on the metal complexes of Yttrium(III) with 5-sulphosalicylic acid; 3,5-dinitro salicylic acid; Sodium 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonate and nitroso-R-salt. The calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique, as used by Irving and Rossotti, has been applied to determine the stepwise protonation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the complexes. The logK values have been computed by alternative methods, at three different temperatures at an ionic strength of 0.2M (NaClO₄).

5-Sulphosalicylic acid (SSA); 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA); Sodium 2, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonate (DHNSA) and nitroso-R salt (NRS) have been reported to yield complexes with various metal ions¹⁻⁷. The present paper reports the potentiometric study of the complexation of yttrium(III) with SSA, DNSA, DHNSA and NRS. "Practical" proton-ligand stability constants of the ligands and metal-ligand stability constants (stepwise) have been determined by the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{8,9} as used by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰.

Experimental

Materials: A stock solution (0.02M) of YCl₃·5H₂O (E. Merck) was prepared in a calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent the hydrolysis and the metal content was estimated. The stock solutions, 0.025M of SSA (Spoldzielnia Pracy), 0.020M of DNSA (E. Merck), 0.010M of DHNSA (L. Light) and 0.020M of NRS (E. Merck) were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantities of pure ligands in double distilled water. The solutions were standardised potentiometrically. Sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) sodium perchlorate (Riedel) and perchloric acid (E. Merck) solutions were prepared in double distilled water and standardised.

Apparatus: A pH-meter (Beckman model H-2) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used. Saturated calomel electrode was connected to the cell externally by means of an agar bridge saturated with KNO₃ to prevent the formation of chloro complexes. The measurement was carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in an electrically maintained thermostat (accuracy ± 0.2°).

Procedure

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the complexes between yttrium(III) and SSA, DNSA, DHNSA and NRS, was determined by potentiometric titration of mixtures of ligands and metal in various ratios, against standard sodium hydroxide (1.0M) solution.

The following four mixtures were prepared in case of SSA and DNSA (ligands).

A : 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand, B : 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 5.0 × 10⁻³ M metal, C : 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 2.5 × 10⁻³ M Metal, D : 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 1.66 × 10⁻³ M metal. Graph of pH vs. the moles of NaOH per mole of ligand (m) was plotted for all the systems.

The following four mixtures were prepared in case of DHNSA and NRS (ligands) :

A : 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand, B : 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal + 2.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand, C : 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal + 3.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand, D : 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal + 4.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand. Graph of pH vs. the moles of NaOH per mole of metal (m) was plotted for these systems.

Bjerrum-Calvin titration for Stability constant :

The three mixtures were prepared as follows :
A : 1.0 × 10⁻² M perchloric acid, B : 1.0 × 10⁻² M perchloric acid + 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand, C : 1.0 × 10⁻² M perchloric acid 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal solution, such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added to maintain the desired ionic strength ($\mu = 0.20$) and the volumes of the mixtures were adjusted to 100 ml using double distilled water. The three titration curves obtained were referred to as (A) acid titration curve (B) ligand titration curve and (C) complex titration curve.

Calculations: The values of \bar{n}_A at various pH have been calculated from the acid and ligand titration curves using equation as given by Irving and Rosotti¹⁰.

The calculation of the "practical" protonation constants was carried out by plotting a graph of \bar{n}_A against pH known as the formation curve of the ligand, and then applying various computational methods¹¹.

The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves drawn between \bar{n} (average number of ligands attached per metal/ion) and pL (free ligand exponent),

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Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry : Y(III)-SSA Complexes : In establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of Y(III) with SSA, the appearance of only one inflection (Fig. 1, curve A) after the addition of 2 moles of base per mole of ligand, corresponds to the complete neutralisation of the two protons, one from sulphonic group and the other from carboxyl group, in a single step. Hence, if free SSA having three replaceable hydrogen ions is denoted as H₃SSA the reaction at m=0.2 may be represented in a single step by equation (1).

Fig. 1: Stoichiometry of Y(III)-SSA complex : Concentration of titrant=1.00M NaOH; Concentration of SSA=5.0 × 10⁻³M. Concentration of Y(III) : Curve A-0.0; Curve B-5.0 × 10⁻³M; Curve C-2.5 × 10⁻³M; Curve D-1.66 × 10⁻³M

The third proton (phenolic) of SSA is not titrable under the experimental conditions. Addition of an equimolar concentration of Y(III) ions (Fig. 1, curve B) alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of complex formation and consequently a considerable shift in the position of the end point is observed. The fall in the initial pH value and an inflection at m ≈ 3 clearly shows that the phenolic proton is displaced due to complexation. This suggests the formation of Y(SSA) as shown in equation (2)

The titration of Y(III) in the presence of two moles of SSA (Fig. 1, curve C) shows an inflection at m ≈ 3 indicating the formation of Y(SSA)₂³⁻. The reaction equilibria may be expressed as,

The formation of these two complexes is further confirmed by the inflection at m ≈ 2.66, when the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 3 (Fig. 1, curve D).

Y(III)-DNSA complexes ; In establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of Y(III) with DNSA, similar four titrations were done as for SSA. When only ligand was titrated, two inflections were obtained at one and two moles of NaOH per mole of ligand respectively (Fig. 2, curve A). The inflections obtained may be due to the reaction taking place according to equations (5) and (6).

Fig. 2: Stoichiometry of Y(III)-DNSA complex : Concentration of titrant=1.00M NaOH; Concentration of DNSA=5.0 × 10⁻³M; Concentration of Y(III) : Curve A-0.0; Curve B-5.0 × 10⁻³M; Curve C-2.5 × 10⁻³M; Curve D-1.66 × 10⁻³M

The titration of Y(III) in the presence of one mole of DNSA shows an inflection at m ≈ 2 (Fig. 2, curve B) indicating the formation of Y(DNSA)⁺. The reaction equilibria may be represented as,

The titration of Y(III) in the presence of two moles of DNSA (Fig. 2, curve C) shows an inflection at $m \approx 2$, showing the formation of $Y(DNSA)_2^-$ as represented by equation (8)

The formation of these two complexes is confirmed by the inflection at $m \approx 1.66$ (eqn. 9) when the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 3 (Fig. 2, curve D). However, the other inflection at $m \approx 2.0$ may be due to the reaction (10). The reaction equilibria may be represented as.

Y(III)-DHNSA and Y(III)-NRS complexes: In case of DHNSA and NRS, the titrations for stoichiometry were done by taking constant metal and varying ligand concentrations. The concentrations employed have been mentioned before. Titrations were done by taking metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 respectively. The inflections were obtained at 2, 4, 6 and 8 moles of NaOH per mole of metal respectively (Fig. 3, curves A, B, C and D) for Y(III)-DHNSA system. This clearly indicates the formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes respectively, complexation taking place through the adjacent phenolic oxygens. The reaction equilibria for the Y(III) DHNSA system may therefore be represented as,

In the case of Y(III)-NRS system, inflections were obtained at 1, 2, 3, and 4 moles of NaOH per mole of metal respectively (Fig. 4, curves A, B, C and D), indicating the formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes. Most probable position of complexation being the nitrogen of the nitroso group and the adjacent phenolic oxygen, which also satisfies the coordination number (six) of the metal. The reaction equilibria may be represented as,

Protonation constants and Stability Constants :

From the titration curves it is observed that the metal-ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve which proves that the liberation of protons is due to chelation. Suitable computational methods were applied to obtain the stepwise proton-ligand stability constants (error limits ± 0.02), and metal-ligand stability constants (error limits ± 0.03). The mean values at an ionic strength of 0.2M (NaClO₄) and at different temperatures have been summarised in Table 1 and Table 2.

Fig. 3 : Stoichiometry of Y(III)-DHNSA complex : Concentration of titrant = 1.00M NaOH ; concentration of Y(III) = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Concentration of DHNSA ; Curve A - $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Curve B - $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Curve C - $3.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Curve D - $4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$

Fig. 4 : Stoichiometry of Y(III)-NRS Complex : Concentration of titrant = 1.00M NaOH ; concentration of Y(III) = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Concentration of NRS. Curve A - $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Curve B - $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Curve C - $3.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; Curve D - $4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$

TABLE 1—VALUE OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS ($\mu = 0.2$)

Ligand	Constants	25°	35°	45°
SSA	$\log K_1^H$	11.01	10.92	10.85
	$\log K_2^H$	2.46	2.48	2.50
	$\log \beta^H$	13.47	13.40	13.35
DNSA	$\log K^H$	6.90	6.80	6.70
	$\log K_1^H$	11.20	11.10	11.01
DHNSA	$\log K_2^H$	7.86	7.77	7.68
	$\log \beta^H$	19.06	18.87	18.69
NRS	$\log K_1^H$	6.79	6.76	6.70

 TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS $\mu = 0.2$

Complex	Constants	25°	35°	45°
Y(III)-SSA	$\log K_1$	7.41	7.36	7.31
	$\log K_2$	5.44	5.40	5.36
	$\log \beta$	12.85	12.76	12.67
Y(III)-DNSA	$\log K_1$	5.70	5.58	5.47
	$\log K_2$	4.35	4.30	4.25
	$\log \beta$	10.05	9.88	9.72
Y(III)-DHNSA	$\log K_1$	9.81	9.62	9.43
	$\log K_2$	7.19	6.91	6.60
	$\log K_3$	3.84	3.60	3.40
	$\log \beta$	20.84	20.13	19.43
Y(III)-NRS	$\log K_1$	4.25	4.15	4.05
	$\log K_2$	3.14	3.02	2.91
	$\log K_3$	2.75	2.71	2.66
	$\log \beta$	10.14	9.88	9.62

Comparing the stabilities of the complexes formed by Yttrium with SSA and DNSA, we find that SSA forms more stable complexes than DNSA. This may be attributed due to the presence of two-NO₂ groups (electron withdrawing) in DNSA, which results in the low basicity of the ligand, and hence the less stability of the DNSA complexes of yttrium. A comparison of the stability of the complexes of yttrium(III) with NRS and DHNSA shows that NRS forms less stable complexes than DHNSA with yttrium. In case of NRS, the

complexation is through the oxime group (-NOH) and in case of DHNSA, the phenolic group (-OH) takes part in complexation. Hence the low stability of NRS complexes may be attributed to the fact that oxime group has got less affinity than phenolic group for the yttrium ion.

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